

MICROSTRUCTURE, MECHANICAL AND TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF AUSTENITIC STAINLESS STEEL COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH TiB₂ PARTICLES

Iwona Sulima

Institute of Technology, Pedagogical University, ul.Podchorazych 2, 30-084 Krakow, Poland

* Corresponding author (isulima@up.krakow.pl)

Keywords: *sintering, composites, titanium diboride (TiB₂), austenitic stainless steel*

1 Introduction

The austenitic stainless steel is widely used in industry owing to their excellent corrosion resistance, heat resistance, oxidation resistance and workability. However, the application of this alloys is restricted by low mechanical properties and poor anti-friction properties [1-3]. Many authors present different approach to strengthening issues of stainless steel. The purpose of this investigations were mainly to improve the mechanical properties of the stainless steel. The literature [4-8] shows that a good way to improve this properties is the incorporation of ceramic particles into the austenitic stainless steel. Moreover, the improvement of the wear resistance of composites can be obtained. Generally, morphology, volume fraction, mode of distribution of various phases and their properties like hardness, strength, cracking tendency and thermal and chemical stability greatly influence the mechanical and tribological properties of composites. Also, applied experimental parameters (pressure, temperature and time) are the significant factors influencing on this properties [8-11].

Many studies were reported on the application of TiB₂ ceramic as reinforcing phase in composites having matrix of iron, copper, aluminium and their alloys [12-18]. Attempts on the development of TiB₂ reinforced stainless steel are only a few. Thong and Lau [19,20] reported on the enhancement of sliding wear and abrasion resistance of AISI 304 stainless steel reinforced with various volume fraction of TiB₂ particles by hot isostatic pressing. The improved wear resistance was attributed to the presence of hard ceramic particles within stainless steel matrix.

Nahme *et al.* [21] studied the mechanical properties of the AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel reinforced with 15 vol.% TiB₂. The improvement of the Young's modulus, tensile strength and compression strength was obtained. However, the strain decreased strongly from 45% to about 6% for the reinforced material. Bacon *et al.* [22] studied fatigue and fracture mechanisms in austenitic stainless steel reinforced with 25 vol. % of TiB₂ particles. A plain strain fracture toughness of 29.6 MPa*m^{0.5} was obtained for this material. This value is significantly lower than that of the 316L parent alloy but is adequate for many engineering applications.

Methods for the production of stainless steel matrix composites reinforced with TiB₂ involve ingot casting and powder metallurgy (PM) processes. The powder metallurgy is ideal to obtain this composites because it provides the dispersion of fine particles [21,23]. The most popular method of obtaining the composites is applying sintering under pressure, for example hot isostatic pressing (HIP) or high pressure-high temperature (HP-HT) method. The application of the HP-HT sintering permits achieving extreme high pressure) and high temperatures simultaneously during the process. Therefore, the sintering process proceeds much faster (usually in several minutes) than free sintering which usually takes few to several hours. The obtained sinters are characterized by a degree of densification reaching almost 100% and isotropic properties. The use of such conditions can also reduce the diffusion of particles and prevent grain growth [24,25].

The high-pressure devices are composed of hydraulic presses and specially-designed chambers that permit sintering. Presently, many solutions for

such high-pressure chambers exist. Basic types of the chambers applied in industry are the following: spherical chambers of Bridgman type, 'Belt' type chambers and multi-die cubic chambers. Such construction solutions of the synthesis chamber allow for relatively large volume of reaction charge, optimal distribution of pressure and achievement of high sintering temperature. Their characteristic feature is attaining quasi-hydrostatic state of stress through stable medium transferring pressure, such as various kinds of rocks, most often. The highest possible temperature at which the sintering process can be carried by means of HP-HT method is 2000°C, or even more – depending on the duration of the sintering process [25,26].

In the present study, the mechanical and tribological properties of sintered 316L austenitic stainless steel reinforced with TiB₂ ceramic were investigated.

2 Experimental procedure

The AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel powder (25 μm, Hoganas) and TiB₂ powder (2.5-3.5 μm, 99.9 wt.%, H.C. Starck) were used in the present study. The stainless-steel powder have the chemical composition as follows: 17.20 wt.% Cr, 12.32 wt.% Ni, 2.02 wt.% Mo, 0.43 wt.% Mn, 0.89 wt.% Si, 0.03 wt.% S, 0.028 wt.% P, 0.03 wt.% C and balance of Fe. wt.%).

The powder were mixed in a turbula mixer for 12 hours. The composites containing 4 and 10 vol.% of TiB₂ were consolidated using the high pressure-high temperature (HP-HT) method. Figure 1 presents the scheme of Bridgman-type HP-HT apparatus. The mixtures were preliminarily consolidated into pellets of diameter 15 mm and height 5 mm under pressure of ~200 MPa. The samples were sintered at temperatures of 1000°C and 1300°C and pressure of 7 ± 0.2 GPa for 60 seconds.

Density was determined by weighing in air and water using Archimedes method. Uncertainty of measurements was 0.02 g/cm³.

Young's moduli of the composites were measured basing on the velocity of the ultrasonic waves transition through the sample using ultrasonic flaw detector Panametrics Epoch III. The accuracy of the calculated Young's modulus was estimated at 2 %.

Sintered samples were prepared by lapping on a cast iron plate with diamond paste and etching. The Vickers indentation tests were performed using FM-7 microhardness tester. The applied load for non-graded materials was 2.942 N. Standard deviations of HV0.3 values were no more than 4 % of the average values.

The compression test was carried out at INSTRON TT-DM machine at strain rate of about of 10⁻³ s⁻¹. The mechanical tests were carried out at room temperature. These tests were performed with specimen of 3 mm in diameter and 4.5 mm in high.

Tribological tests were carried out using the UMT-2T (producer CETR, USA) Ball-on-disk tribotester. Tests were carried out without lubricant according to the ISO 20808:2004(E). For ball-on-disk method the sliding contact is brought by pushing a ball on a rotating disc specimen under a constant load (Fig.2). The loading mechanism applies a controlled load F_n to the ball holder. The friction force was measured continuously during the test using the extensometer.

Fig.1 Scheme of Bridgman-type, toroidal HP-HT apparatus: 1 – anvil (A – central part made of sintered carbides, B – supporting steel rings), 2– pyrophyllite container, 3 – pyrophyllite gasket, 4 – material for sintering , 5 – punch, 6 – supporting plate [25]

Fig.2. Schematic of the Ball-on-disk wear test system [27].

For each test a new ball is used. Specimens are washed in high purity acetone and dried. After mounting the ball and sample, materials are washed in ethyl alcohol and then dried. Ball was made of Al_2O_3 with diameter of 3.175 mm. The tests were conducted at room temperature under load of 4 N for sliding speed of 0.1 m/s and a total sliding distance of 100 m. Duration of a test was 1000 s.

For morphological characterization of the composites JEOL JSM 6610LV scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used. EDS technique (AZtec) was applied to determine the chemical composition of sintered composites. Also, the phase compositions of selected samples were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation with a scintillation detector (Bruker Discover D8).

3 Results

The density of the composites as a function of TiB_2 addition amount are presented in Fig.3. At the applied conditions of sintering, composites with a very high level of consolidation were obtained. The density values are 95-100% of theoretical density. It can be seen that the densification increases for composites with 4% vol. of TiB_2 . However, the

application 10% vol. of TiB_2 ceramic causes the reduction of density.

An effect of TiB_2 addition on the Young's modulus and hardness of composites is illustrated in Figs.4 and 5. It was observed that the Young's modulus increases with the increasing content of TiB_2 phase. In case of the composite with 10% vol. of TiB_2 , the Young modulus are 207 GPa and 210 GPa for temperature of 1000°C and 1300°C , respectively. For comparison, the Young's modulus of the austenitic stainless steel are 184 GPa and 190 GPa, respectively.

Fig.3 Variation of density with TiB_2 content for sintered composites.

Fig.4 The results of the Young's modulus of composites as a function of TiB_2 content.

Fig.5 The results of the microhardness of composites as a function TiB₂ content.

Fig.7 The friction coefficient of composites containing various content of TiB₂.

Fig.6. The results of the compression tests for the austenitic AISI 316L stainless steel and steel-TiB₂ composites.

Similarly, the microhardness of the composites increased with increasing the TiB₂ content in the steel matrix. It is seen that the microhardness is higher for composites sintered at lower temperature. The microhardness are 435 HV0.3 and 402 HV0.3 for composites with 10% vol. sintered at 1000°C and 1300°C, respectively. However, for the unreinforced steel which was sintered at the same temperatures, the microhardness receives values of 340 HV0.3 and 223 HV0.3, respectively. The improvement of microhardness is a result of the dispersion strengthening by TiB₂ particles in the steel matrix. This effect is attributed to the higher hardness of the TiB₂ particles.

Fig.8 Variation of specific wear rate with TiB₂ content for sintered composites

Figure 6 shows the influence of content of TiB₂ and temperature on the compression strength. The increase of the compression strength with the increase of TiB₂ phase content was observed. The highest compression strength was obtained for the composite with 10 vol. % TiB₂ which was sintered at temperature of 1300°C. In the case of these materials, the 0.2% proof strength (R_{0.2}) has the highest values, it is equal to 1185 MPa.

In Figure 7, friction coefficient (μ) measured using ball-on-disc method is presented. The decrease of the friction coefficient of the sintered composites with increasing TiB₂ content was observed.

a)

b)

c)

Fig.9 Microstructure of the: a) AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel and composites: b) 4 vol.% TiB_2 and c) 10 vol.% TiB_2 (after sintering at $1300^\circ C$).

a)

b)

c)

Fig.10 (a) SEM micrograph of composites with 4 vol.% TiB_2 sintered at $1300^\circ C$ and (b,c) the corresponding EDS analyses at the selected points.

Fig.11 SEM micrograph of composites with 10 vol.% TiB_2 sintered at $1300^\circ C$.

The friction coefficient of composites with 10% vol. TiB_2 is about 20-25% lower in comparison to the austenitic stainless steel. The lowest value of the friction coefficient have composites with 10% vol. TiB_2 , it is equal to 0.5 (for samples sintered at $1300^\circ C$). It can be seen from Figure 8 that increasing the content of TiB_2 in matrix causes a lower wear rate compared to pure austenitic stainless steel. In composite, material removal is limited because there is an accumulation of TiB_2 particles on the surface after the steel having been removed during the sliding. In effect, the improvement of wear resistance was observed. It was also observed that the tribological properties of composites depend on the sintering temperature. Generally, for temperature of $1300^\circ C$ friction coefficients and smaller wear rates were obtained lower.

The typical microstructure of the austenitic stainless steel and discussed composites with different content TiB_2 are shown in Figures 9-11. Microstructure observations revealed that TiB_2 particles with an average size of 3-6 μm are homogeneously distributed in the steel matrix. However, the formation the agglomeration of TiB_2 practices was observed locally. The EDS analyses confirmed the presence of TiB_2 along the grain boundaries in all the sintered composites (Fig.12). Similarly, Figure 13 presents the XRD results of sintered composites, characterized only by the presence of TiB_2 in steel matrix. There is no indication of formation of a new phase.

Fig.12 SEM microstructure of composites with 10 vol.% TiB_2 (sintered at $1300^\circ C$) and line scans analysis for Ti, B, Fe, Cr, N, Mo and Mn.

Fig.13. X-ray diffraction pattern of the sintered materials obtained at temperature of 1300°C and pressure of 7 GPa.

4 Conclusions

Two variants of the steel-TiB₂ composites with 4 vol.% and 10 vol.% of TiB₂ phase were obtained by high pressure–high temperature (HP-HT) method.

The application of a larger participation of strengthening phase improves the properties of the sintered materials. The composites with 10 vol.% TiB₂ sintered by HP-HT method provide the attractive combination of physical and mechanical properties. The results show that this composites exhibited higher Young's modulus, Vickers hardness and compression strength in comparison to conventionally austenitic AISI 316L stainless steel. The wear resistance of the steel-TiB₂ composites improved with the increase of the content of TiB₂.

The results suggest that the temperature of only 1000°C is sufficient for good quality of HP-HT sintering of these composites.

5 Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge Prof L. Jaworska Ph.D., D.Sc., P. Figiel, Ph.D. and P. Klimczyk, Ph.D. from the Institute of Advanced Manufacturing Technology in Cracow, Poland for discussions and assistance in carrying out the experiments.

The study was performed under Research Project No. N N507 222840 (No. 2228/B/T02/2011/40).

References

- [1] S. Lin W. Xiong, Microstructure and abrasive behaviors of TiC-316L composites prepared by warm compaction and microwave sintering, *Advanced Powder Technology*, Vol. 23, pp. 419-425, 2012
- [2] C.J. Novak, D. Peckner, I.M. Bernstein (Eds.), *Handbook of stainless steels*, McGraw-Hill, New York, pp. 23–45, 1977
- [3] D.M. Jyotsna, K. Ajeet, L. Li, Direct laser cladding of SiC dispersed AISI 316L stainless steel. *Tribological International*, Vol. 42, pp. 750–753, 2009
- [4] M. Vardavoullus, M. Jeandin, F. Velasco, J.M. Torralba, Dry sliding wear mechanism for P/M austenitic stainless steels and their composites containing Al₂O₃ and Y₂O₃ particles, *Tribology International*, Vol. 29, No.6, pp. 499-506, 1996
- [5] A. Farid, S. Guo, F. Cui, P. Feng, T. Lin, TiB₂ and TiC stainless steel matrix composites, *Materials Letters*, Vol.61, pp. 189-191, 2000
- [6] A. K. Srivastava, K. Das, The abrasive wear resistance of TiC and (Ti,W)C-reinforced Fe–17Mn austenitic steel matrix composites, *Tribology International*, Vol. 43, Issues 5–6, pp. 944-950, 2010
- [7] Z.F. Ni, Y.S. Sun, F. Xue, J. Bai, Y.J. Lu, Microstructure and properties of austenitic stainless steel reinforced with in situ TiC particulate, *Materials & Design*, Vol. 32, Issue 3, pp. 1462-1467, 2011
- [8] I. Sulima, L. Jaworska, P. Figiel, Influence of processing parameters and different content of TiB₂ ceramics on the properties of composites sintered by high temperature –high pressure (HT-HP) method, *Archives of Metallurgy and Materials*, Vol. 59, no.1, 2014 (in press)
- [9] E. Pagounis, V.K. Lindroos: Processing and properties of particulate reinforced steel matrix composites, *Materials Science and Engineering A246*, pp. 221–234, 1998
- [11] A.D. Panasyuk, A.P. Umansky, Phase evolution in the iron–TiB₂ system, *Journal of the Less Common Metals*, Vol. 117, pp. 335–339, 1986
- [12] I. Sulima, P. Klimczyk, P. Hyjek, The influence of the sintering conditions on the properties of the stainless steel reinforced with TiB₂ ceramics,

Archives of Materials Science and Engineering, Vol.39, No 2, pp.103-106, 2009

[13] A. Animesh, T.K. Bandyopadhyay, K. Das, Synthesis and characterization of TiB₂-reinforced iron-based composites, Journal of Materials Processing Technology Vol.172, pp. 70–76, 2006.

[14] S.C. Tjong, K., F. Tam, Mechanical and thermal expansion behavior of hiped aluminium-TiB₂ composites, Materials Chemistry and Physics, Vol. 97, pp. 91-97, 2006

[15] A. Anal, T.K. Bandyopadhyay, K. Das, Synthesis and characterization of TiB₂-reinforced iron-based composites, Journal of Materials Processing Technology, Vol., 172, pp. 70–76, 2006

[16] M.A. Einarrud, E. Hagen, G. Pettersen, T. Grande, Pressureless sintering of titanium diboride with nickel, nickel boride, and iron additives, Journal of the American Ceramic Society Vol.80, No.12, pp. 3013–3020, 1997

[17] Y. Zhang, N. Ma, H. Wang, Y. Le, X. Li, Damping capacity of in situ TiB₂ particulates reinforced aluminium composites with Ti addition, Materials and Design, Vol.28, pp. 628–632, 2007

[18] E. Frasz, A. Janas, P. Kurtyka, S. Wierzbinski: Structure and properties of cast Ni₃Al/TiC and Ni₃Al/TiB₂ composites. PART II. Investigation of mechanical and tribological properties and of corrosion resistance of composites based on intermetallic phase Ni₃Al reinforced with particles of TiC and TiB₂. Archives of Metallurgy and Materials, vol. 49, Issues 1., pp.113-141, 2004

[19] Tjong S.C., Lau K.C. “Abrasion resistance of stainless-steel composites reinforced with hard TiB₂ particles”, Composites Science and Technology, Vol. 60, pp. 1141-1146, 2000

[20] Tjong S.C., Lau K.C, Sliding wear of stainless steel matrix composite reinforced with TiB₂ particles, Materials Letter, Vol.41, pp.153-158, 1999

[21] Nahme H., Lach E., Tarran A., “Mechanical property under high dynamic loading and microstructure evaluation of a TiB₂ particle-reinforced stainless steel” Journal of Materials Science, vol. 44, pp. 463-468, 2009

[22] D.H. Bacon, L. Edwards, J.E. Moffatt, M.E. Fitzpatri, Fatigue and fracture of a 316 stainless steel metal matrix composite reinforced with 25% titanium diboride, International Journal of Fatigue, Vol. 8, pp. 39-47, 2013

[23] Metals Handbook, 9th edn., Vol.7, American Society for Metals, pp.710-716, 1984

[24] I. Sulima, P. Figiel, M. Susniak, M. Swiątek, Sintering of TiB₂ ceramic, Archives of Materials Science and Engineering, Vol. 28, No.11 pp. 687-690, 2007

[25] L. Jaworska, Receiving and application of diamond in machining, WNT, Warsaw, 2007

[26] M.I. Eremts, High pressure experimental method. Oxford:Oxford University Press, 1996,

[27] Figiel P., Zimowski S., Klimczyk P., Dziwisz T., Jaworska L., Mechanical and tribological properties of TiC-based composites for ED machining, Archives of Materials Science and Engineering, Vol. 33, Issue 2, pp. 83-88, 2008